

BUILDING AN INTEGUMENTARY SYSTEM HYPERSPECTRAL MODEL FOR AVATARS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we transform the results of a hyperspectral skin reflectance model into RGB values to simulate the color of skin under various biological circumstances. The amount of different chromophores in the skin can be adjusted within the model to simulate circumstances such as elevated blood levels in the cheeks caused by blushing, the draining of blood from the face caused by fear, or the bluish tint of the skin caused by a lack of oxygen. The melanosome level in the epidermis can also be adjusted to simulate different levels of skin darkness and show how increased levels of melanosomes reduce the influence of other chromophores in skin.

Index Terms— integumentary system, skin, hyperspectral modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

Modeling can be an important function in gaining a deeper understanding of an object of interest. In our work, we are interested in generating aspects of an avatar, limited to modeling those aspects that may be detected in a remotely sensed application such as search and rescue, homeland security efforts at national airports, and other law enforcement functions. Our proposition of an avatar is not a stretch of the imagination and has already been accomplished to different degrees by other researchers [1].

An avatar has at least two important uses. First in a detection scenario, one can measure the attributes of specific interest and apply those to the model, which can be exploited for functions such as search and rescue or a remote “lie detector”. The second aspect is that of building a realistic avatar that can be exploited for building exploitation algorithms, driving sensor design for specific detection tasks, and in general understanding the visual effects of the “human response.” The remainder of this article emphasizes the

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second aspect through a physics-based model of human skin and demonstrates how certain conditions manifest in the spectra and how they appear through an RGB sensor.

2. AVATAR

2.1. A human skin model

A human skin reflectance model for the near-infrared (NIR) portion of the electromagnetic spectrum was developed in [2] based on the skin reflectance measurements from cadavers and living persons as well as a literature review of the optical parameters of human skin’s constituent components. This model is extended into the visible (VIS) portion of the electromagnetic spectrum and considers additional chromophores such as hemoglobin, bilirubin, and beta-carotene. Figure 1 shows the results for the model for various epidermal melanosome levels, blood volumes, and hemoglobin oxygenation levels in the skin. Beyond the VIS, the only significant chromophores are the melanosomes of the epidermis.

Fig. 1. VIS and NIR skin reflectance model results for various melanosome levels in the epidermis, levels of hemoglobin oxygenation, and various blood volumes in the skin.

2.2. The RGB response of the avatar

In order to color the avatar skin pixels, spectra are generated from our physics-based model for each skin pixel and converted to the RGB color space. The response of each pixel is parameterized based on the desired effect of that pixel. For example, one may determine RGB values transformed from the skin reflectance model based on different blood volumes, hemoglobin oxygenation levels within blood, or epidermal melanosome levels.

For the cheek regions, it is assumed that melanosome levels and hemoglobin oxygenation levels are the same as the rest of the face. In this article, we wish to increase blood volume in the cheeks to give a rosy cheek effect. To simulate this effect, a Gaussian gradient for blood volume is used between the highest cheek value and the value for the rest of the face. This is done to give a more realistic depiction of blood distribution in these regions.

Since the reflectance spectra tell us how much of the incident light energy is reflected from the skin surface, they are scaled using a matrix of intensity values to account for lighting effects in the environment. These intensity values are based on a gray-scale version of the original image normalized to one. In this way, shadows and facial features are preserved in the final avatar.

Creating realistic skin color involves a transformation of the spectra generated by the skin reflectance model into the RGB color space. The spectra are first transformed into the CIE 1931 XYZ color space which is defined by the International Commission on Illumination (CIE) [3]. The inner product of the spectra and each of the three functions that describe the XYZ color space reduces the full spectrum model to three values. This resulting vector of values is then multiplied by a 3×3 matrix to transform the XYZ color space into the RGB color space [4].

Model input parameters are easily changed to incorporate additional regions to the avatar for study (e.g. bruises, rashes, or freckles). Assumptions of uniform melanosome level and blood oxygenation level parameters are for modeling simplicity only. Non-uniform distributions of chromophores as well as the adjustment of the volume of chromophores such as bilirubin and beta-carotene can be used to increase the realism of the results.

The avatar used for this work is based on an image created by DAZ Productions, Incorporated [5]. This work does not generate spectra for the eyes, lips, or the avatar's background environment. Those regions retain the color of the original avatar image. Figure 2 shows a color image of an avatar based on the RGB colors calculated from a spectra assuming a 2% melanosome level with a baseline volume of blood throughout most of the face and three times the baseline level of blood in the cheeks. The right pane of the figure shows the reflectance spectra used to derive the color of the face and cheeks. There is a noticeable decrease in reflectance in the cheek portion of

the spectra from 350nm to 600nm which will be discussed in Section 3 of this article.

Fig. 2. Avatar with a 2% melanosome level and increased blood volume in the cheek. Corresponding reflectance spectra presented in the right pane.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Epidermal Melanosomes

The melanin pigment is contained in cells throughout the epidermis called melanosomes. The percentage of melanosomes in the epidermis of skin accounts for most of the difference in skin color among different groups of people [6]. The melanosome volume varies from 1.6 – 6.3% for a fair-skinned person, 11 – 16% for a moderately pigmented person, and 18 – 43% for a darkly pigmented person [7]. It is important to note a linear increase in melanosomes does not correspond to a linear increase in skin darkness. As the melanosome level increases its effect on skin darkness begins to decrease.

As stated previously, Fig. 2 shows the avatar face with a 2% melanosome level. Due to the low melanosome level in this face, the blush of the cheeks is clearly visible. The top of Fig. 3 shows the results for 4% and 8% melanosome levels while the bottom shows the results for a 16% and 32% melanosome level for the avatar. It is clearly evident that as melanosome level increases, the ability to differentiate the blush of the cheek from the rest of the skin diminishes. The right pane of Fig. 3 shows the effect increasing the melanosome level has on skin reflectance. As the melanosome level increases, reflectance decreases over the entire spectrum. This decrease is reduced for larger versus smaller wavelengths.

3.2. Blood volume

Dilation of the vascular system is due to the regulation of the nervous system and due to embarrassment or anger [8]. Nervous system regulatory mechanisms that cause vasodilation in the skin are typically caused by the bodies attempt to

Fig. 3. Top: Left and right halves of avatar correspond to 4% and 8% melanosome levels with corresponding reflectance spectra in the right pane. **Bottom:** Left and right half of avatar correspond to 16% and 32% melanosome levels with corresponding reflectance spectra presented in the right pane.

maintain and regulate temperature. This can occur if the skin temperature decreases below some acceptable value where the body is attempting to warm the skin to prevent damage and also occurs when the body attempts to cool the body down due to physical exertion.

The typical cases of vasodilation are evocable. That is to say, its rather simple to force vasodilation as a response to cooling the body or heating extremities exposed to cold. What may be more interesting to model is vasodilatation as a response to embarrassment (due to a release of adrenaline). It most often appears in the face and upper thorax region (upper chest), although the particular manifestation depends on the individual. The centers of the cheeks for the avatars in Fig. 3 show the effect of tripling the blood volume in the skin, simulating vasodilation. The right panes of Fig. 3 show the reflectance differences as a result of different blood volumes in the skin at different melanosome levels. As the blood volume increases in the skin, the characteristic *w*-shape at 585nm caused by oxygenated hemoglobin within blood becomes more visible and the blue and green portions of the VIS are further suppressed. A higher melanosome level in the skin suppresses the effect of the chromophores of blood until

their effect is negligible for a darkly pigmented person.

Trauma to the skin such as sunburn or an abrasion can result in increased blood volume near the surface of the skin. The left side of Fig. 4 shows the result of ten times the normal blood volume in the skin with a 2% melanosome level. At this blood volume, the skin begins to take on a distinctly reddish tint. The right pane of Fig. 4 shows the manifestation of increasing the blood volume on the reflectance spectra. The characteristic *w*-shape of oxygenated hemoglobin and the suppression of the blue and green portions of the reflectance becomes even more significant as the blood volume increases.

Fig. 4. Top: Avatar with a 2% melanosome level and corresponding reflectance spectra presented in the right pane. **Bottom:** Avatar with an 8% melanosome level and corresponding reflectance spectra in the right pane. The left half has normal blood volume except for the cheek which has an increased blood volume. The right half of the avatars are void of blood.

Constriction of blood vessels is regulated by the nervous system and can be influenced by hormonal mechanisms [8]. Hormonal mechanisms are due to the release of epinephrine and small amounts of norepinephrine which can be a sympathetic nervous system response to physical exertions (e.g., exercise) [8]. One example of this would be fear evoking the “fight-or-flight” response causing vasoconstriction in the integumentary system to route blood to organs that need it.

Death can also cause the blood volume in skin to decrease. For example, gravity may cause blood to drain from the

surface of the skin eliminating the pinkish hue caused by hemoglobin. The right side of the two avatar images in Fig. 4 (top left and bottom left) demonstrate the absence of blood in the skin. The right panes of Fig. 4 (top right and bottom right) show the skin reflectance for skin with normal and increased blood volume and no blood in the skin. Hemoglobin absorption in the blue and green portions of the VIS is no longer present which gives the right side of the face a paler look.

3.3. Hemoglobin oxygenation

Another important aspect of this work is to characterize the color of skin based on the hemoglobin oxygenation level. This has important implications in search and rescue applications providing some level of triage. Hemoglobin typically has a 75% oxygenation level. This mixture results from arteries carrying approximately 100% oxygenated hemoglobin from the lungs and veins returning a mixture of approximately 50% oxygenated hemoglobin and 50% deoxygenated hemoglobin to the lungs for oxygenation.

Figure 5 shows the avatar with a 2% melanosome level. The left and right sides of the avatar have a hemoglobin oxygenation level of 75% and 0% respectively while the right pane of the figure shows the associated reflectance spectra. The most obvious difference between the two sides of the avatar is in the cheeks which have ten times the normal blood volume. The cheek on the left side has a reddish tint while the cheek on the right side has the distinctly bluish tint associated with oxygen deprivation. As indicated in the spectra of Fig. 3, as the melanosome level increases, the ability to detect the presence of oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin decreases. The right pane of Fig. 5 shows the skin reflectance spectra for skin with and without oxygenated hemoglobin. When none of the hemoglobin in the blood is oxygenated, skin has a lower reflectance in the red portion of the VIS and the *w*-shape at 585nm is not present.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

This article presents an avatar where the integumentary system is created using a physics-based hyperspectral model. The model allows one to generate accurate colors for skin with varying epidermal melanosome levels, blood volume, and hemoglobin oxygenation levels. Secondly, it hints that hyperspectral imagers may potentially be used to unobtrusively characterize persons of interest, say in a security or medical setting. In the latter case, conditions such as anemia (causes reduced hemoglobin), jaundice (causes increased bilirubin), or polycythemia (causes increased hemoglobin) can be modeled and possibly measured remotely.

In this article, we simulate an RGB sensor response by converting the hyperspectral skin reflectance model output to a RGB image. In this vein, future efforts could resample

Fig. 5. Avatar with a 2% melanosome level. The left and right half of the avatar have a hemoglobin oxygenation level of 75% and 0% respectively. Corresponding reflectance spectra presented in the right pane.

the modeled reflectance spectra based on the response of a desired sensor. The benefit to this is two-fold. First, it allows one to determine sensor requirements. Second, it allows one to determine if an existing (and possibly expensive) sensor performs in an acceptable manner. Additional future work could consider different lighting conditions in order to better estimate the expected sensor response (i.e. incorporating the irradiance of sunlight, incandescent lighting, fluorescent lighting, etc.).

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